

THE INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING SPEAKING**Toshtimerova Nurjayna Chintemerovna***Navoi State Pedagogical institute,**English language and literature faculty student*Scientific adviser **Istamova Dilnoza Sadullayevna**

Annotation: This article provides information how speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching. In order to teach second language learners how to speak in the best way possible, some speaking activities are provided below, that can be applied to ESL and EFL classroom settings, together with suggestions for teachers who teach oral language.

Key words: speaking, brainstorming, storytelling, interviews, role play, reporting.

What is meant by "teaching speaking" is to teach ESL learners to:

- Produce the English speech sounds and sound patterns
- Use word and sentence stress, intonation patterns and the rhythm of the second language.
- Select appropriate words and sentences according to the proper social setting, audience, situation and subject matter.
- Organize their thoughts in a meaningful and logical sequence.
- Use language as a means of expressing values and judgments.
- Use the language quickly and confidently with few unnatural pauses, which is called as fluency.

Here are some useful activities in teaching speaking:

Role Play

One other way of getting students to speak is role-playing. Students pretend they are in various social contexts and have a variety of social roles. In role-play activities,

the teacher gives information to the learners such as who they are and what they think or feel. Thus, the teacher can tell the student that "You are David, you go to the doctor and tell him what happened last night, and..."

Information Gap

In this activity, students are supposed to be working in pairs. One student will have the information that other partner does not have and the partners will share their information. Information gap activities serve many purposes such as solving a problem or collecting information. Also, each partner plays an important role because the task cannot be completed if the partners do not provide the information the others need. These activities are effective because everybody has the opportunity to talk extensively in the target language.

Brainstorming

On a given topic, students can produce ideas in a limited time. Depending on the context, either individual or group brainstorming is effective and learners generate ideas quickly and freely. The good characteristics of brainstorming is that the students are not criticized for their ideas so students will be open to sharing new ideas.

Storytelling

Students can briefly summarize a tale or story they heard from somebody beforehand, or they may create their own stories to tell their classmates. Story telling fosters creative thinking. It also helps students express ideas in the format of beginning, development, and ending, including the characters and setting a story has to have. Students also can tell riddles or jokes. For instance, at the very beginning of each class session, the teacher may call a few students to tell short riddles or jokes as an opening. In this way, not only will the teacher address students' speaking ability, but also get the attention of the class.

Interviews

Students can conduct interviews on selected topics with various people. It is a good idea that the teacher provides a rubric to students so that they know what type of

questions they can ask or what path to follow, but students should prepare their own interview questions. Conducting interviews with people gives students a chance to practice their speaking ability not only in class but also outside and helps them becoming socialized. After interviews, each student can present his or her study to the class. Moreover, students can interview each other and "introduce" his or her partner to the class.

Story Completion

This is a very enjoyable, whole-class, free-speaking activity for which students sit in a circle. For this activity, a teacher starts to tell a story, but after a few sentences he or she stops narrating. Then, each student starts to narrate from the point where the previous one stopped. Each student is supposed to add from four to ten sentences. Students can add new characters, events, descriptions and so on.

Reporting

Before coming to class, students are asked to read a newspaper or magazine and, in class, they report to their friends what they find as the most interesting news. Students can also talk about whether they have experienced anything worth telling their friends in their daily lives before class.

Picture Narrating

This activity is based on several sequential pictures. Students are asked to tell the story taking place in the sequential pictures by paying attention to the criteria provided by the teacher as a rubric. Rubrics can include the vocabulary or structures they need to use while narrating.

Find the Difference

For this activity students can work in pairs and each couple is given two different pictures, for example, picture of boys playing football and another picture of girls playing tennis. Students in pairs discuss the similarities and/or differences in the pictures.

Used literatures:

1. Celce-Murcia. M. 2001. Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language (3rd ed). USA: Heinle&Heinle.
2. Chaney, A.L., and T.L. Burk. 1998. Teaching Oral Communication in Grades K-8. Boston: Allyn&Bacon.
3. Aldashev, I. T., Komilova, Z. K., & Nazirjonova, F. S. (2021). THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Экономика и социум*, (2-1), 49-52.
4. Komilova, Z. K., & Nazirjonova, F. S. (2021). THE ROLE OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGYIES IN EDUCATION. *Экономика и социум*, (4-1), 167-170.
5. Yusufjonova, S. M. (2022). PHRASAL VERBS WITH “HEART” IN GERMAN AND OTHER FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Open Access Repository*, 8(1), 109-117.
6. Yusufjonova, S. M. (2019). Set phrases in German language. *International Journal of Student Research*, (3), 80-83.
7. Yusufjonova, S. (2020). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASES IN UZBEK AND GERMAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (2), 590-592.
8. Гафуров, Б. З. ТЕКСТЫ С ФОНОСТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИМИ ФОНОВАРИАНТАМИ И ИХ ПЕРЕВОД (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА). *ILIM hám JÁMIYET*, 72.
9. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). The Theme of Female Gender in the Texts of Advertising in Russian and Uzbek Languages (On the Material of Medical Vocabulary). *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 23-29.
10. Gafurov, B. Z. (2022). Analysis of medical version in texts of advertising of hygiene products in the fight against COVID-19 (on the material of Russian and Uzbek languages). *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*.

11. Gafurov, B. Z. Similarities and differences of segment background options for Russian, Uzbek and English languages. *Monografia pokonferency jnascience, Research, development*, 26, 17-19.
12. Shodiyeva, G., & Ismatova, S. (2022). O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO'Z TURKUMLARI MASALASI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(7), 103-105.
13. qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINCIPILES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).
14. Shodiyeva, G. N. K., & Dustmatov, H. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 234-237.
15. Do'smatov, D. qizi Shodiyeva, GN (2022, May). O 'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH.
16. Qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINCIPILES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).